

Noah's Ark

A Reprieve from Annihilation, Not from the Ordeal

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[سفينة نوح، طوق نجاة لا معراج خلاص](#)

Speech fell silent. White flags were raised. Mankind was left helpless. The final verdict was passed elsewhere. The grave matter was soon to come to pass. There is no averting the wrath of the Heavens. It is inevitable, comprehensive, with no mercy or exception. For the earth seethed with corruption and falsehood, and clamored with misguidance and denial. The angels departed the face of the earth and sought refuge with the Lord of the Heavens. Now, upon the earth, there are none but devils from among the jinn and mankind.

The Heavens received permission from their Creator, so they flashed with lightning. And they pummeled the earth with a torrential downpour. They clothed it in mountains of water and fire. They stripped it of life and washed away the filth and disgrace upon it. They left upon it no creature, great or small, except those whom its Lord permitted and granted refuge. And upon a wooden structure atop sheets of water, a few righteous ones were securely gathered. In pairs: humans, beasts, birds, and plants, selected and chosen by their Creator.

And Man is Saved

Man did it again, and was saved. This weak creature managed to conquer death. This intruder managed to cling to the earth, though he has no roots. Many creatures perished and vanished, but he endured. They were stronger than him, yet they lowered their flags and vanished. They could not bear the changing temperament of nature, so they departed and vanished. They could not endure death, which forever

crouches, so they chose rest and vanished. They could not bear the tyranny of existence, so they chose non-existence and vanished.

Since the dawn of history, man has been writing it time and again. He always lives the inevitability of annihilation, and is saved. The causes of annihilation are imminent, enveloping the place, and he is saved. The precursors of death are too numerous to count, and he is saved. Annihilation is a beast that sinks fangs and stifles breath, and he is saved. Annihilation is an earthquake that levels mountains and splits the earth's crust, and he is saved. Annihilation is a volcano that spews flame and scorches the plains, and he is saved. Annihilation is a blazing fire that scorches stone and blights crops, and he is saved. Annihilation is a pestilence that ravages and a famine that squeezes, and he is saved.

God's Promise

It is a word spoken by the Almighty, and it became a law and a statute. For He willed it to be a homeland for man for a time. And He willed him to be a sovereign and a vicegerent therein for a time. And until God wills otherwise, man remains the master of this earth. And the earth, no matter how intense its anger and how constrained it is by its inhabitant, never deviates from the statute of its Master and Creator. Likewise, the calamities, no matter how loud their cry, and no matter how its face contorts with anger, they are subordinate to His will, without sin or disobedience.

God Almighty alone is the Protector, the Guarantor of man's existence. He granted him the means to manage his affairs, whatever was made available to him. And when the balance is disrupted and the scale of annihilation tilts, the latter remembers God's promise, so it rectifies and recedes. There is no changing the will or decree of God.

The Dualities of Anxiety and Impairment

Gathering existential contradictions into anatomical units gives rise to the language of dualities. They are too numerous to count; such as the dualities of life and death, good and evil, health and sickness, white and black, security and danger, to the end of those selected pairs. And binding them with the contract of meaning reveals the concept of anxiety and impairment. For life is extinguished by death, good is kicked by evil, health is wounded by sickness, security is shaken by danger, and white is

troubled by black. Adding the linguistic dimension to the functional one gives the dualities of anxiety and impairment their meaning.

The dualities of anxiety and impairment are existential dualities that shape human history. Indeed, they are man himself. They were created when he was created, and they settled where he settled. And I swear they will remain as long as man remains a duality of body and soul. They are the engine for man's evolution, the regulator for the rhythm of his life. They catch him between the two planks of their swing since his birth. And they do not leave him except when he becomes a singularity of a body with no spirit within.

Man was Created Weak

Man was created weak, and thus he remains forever, burdened by the dualities of his weakness and anxiety. God's promise guaranteed man's survival and shielded him from the inevitability of annihilation. As for his salvation [from the ordeal of life], God entrusted it to man himself. He did not leave him unarmed. He provided him with the means, bestowed upon him intellect, and did not grudge him messengers for guidance and moral direction. And He left him thereafter to discern for himself the paths to his salvation and the elevators of his spirit.

God has always saved man from the destroyers of time, and He will continue to save him for as long as He wills. However, after every crisis, He would return him to his first primal state, where weakness and anxiety perpetually reside, in the guise of voracious dualities that consume him throughout the epochs and ages.

God Almighty Said:

"Until when Our command came and the oven overflowed, We said, 'Load upon it of each [kind] two mates and your family, except those against whom the word has preceded, and whoever has believed.' But none had believed with him, except a few." (Surah Hud, 11:40-41).

The statement, in which there is no ambiguity, was written. It was inscribed with letters of light, in which there is no extinction. Should you, O man, ascend to the surface of this expanse, you are saved and being saved. And carry with you the provision of your existential dualities, and do not leave behind a single pair. For you

will remain, and they will remain likewise, companions of place and associates of time. You will remain as long as existence remains, and they will remain likewise. Remaining, but always shrouded in the dualities of your weakness and anxiety. They toss you mercilessly between their two planks. No sooner do you doze off on its gentle palm, than its harsh one kicks you to awaken, for you are destined for misery. So you awake from a rosy dream that lasted but a little while.

The raging forces of nature will not defeat you, nor the predators of the wild, nor will the enfeeblers of the soul or the burdeners of the spirit overcome you. But they will, nonetheless, continue to demolish thrones over which you are the master, and undermine edifices that you have built. There is no escape from them, no way out... They are the necessary conditions of your ordeal and your test. They are your preoccupations, the impetus of thought and the inspirers of the soul. If the fire of their furnace melts you, it purges you of impurity. Or if the hammer of their anvil folds you, it polishes your resolve. Or did you think that you would attain virtue and be guided to salvation while you are free from such burdens and from those ordeals?

Important Note:

For an overflow of similar meanings, please refer to another article of mine by clicking on the following link:

[Absurd Wars: The Dualities of Existential Anxiety... Eternal Torment or a Sustained Test? \(DOI\)](#)

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